

Demographic Changes and Replacement Migration in Kerala

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Abstract

Kerala, a state of southern India is witnessing large inflow of migrant labour from different parts of the country in the recent years. One of the main reasons for such a trend is the demographic and social character of the state. Kerala is one of the states in India which ranks highest with respect to social and human indices. Kerala experiencing an advanced demographic transition as the mortality and fertility levels have come down. During 1950 -60 the life expectancy at birth for Kerala were only 46.15 years which advanced to 75.2 years during 2011-15. The aged population constitute 13.3 % of the total population 2016. This changes in the demographic structure leads a shortage of labours born out of demographic transition and increase the number of aged people in the state. The recent phenomenon of replacement migration is a result of a rapid decline in the number of workers in the young working ages caused by the demographic transition, emigration of a large number of young person's to the gulf countries and the aversion of youth towards the low paid unskilled jobs. The shortage of labours as a result of ageing population and out-migration is met by labourers from other parts of the country. In this context, the present study focuses the reasons that are responsible for the evolution of replacement migration, along with the consequences resulting out of it. The study makes use of secondary data for meeting the objectives.

Keywords: migration, demographic transition, replacement migration

Introduction

Individual migration is the movement by people from one place to another with the intentions of settling, permanently or temporarily in a new location. The movement of people in look for of better living situation and a more protected environment is as old as human civilisation. Such movements not only change the lives of the migrants deeply but also lead to major economic and social changes both at the place of origin and destination of the migrants. The development in the transport and communication sectors along with industrialisation have smoothed the way for large-scale movements of people from villages to towns, from towns to other towns and from one country to another country in search of new job opportunities. Industrialisation has widened the gap between rural and urban areas, inducing a shift of the workforce towards industrialising areas (Arun and Ajay, 2017).

Migration from Kerala to the other states in India and to countries outside has now become so rampant that its impact is felt in every aspect of life in the State. (K.C.Zachariah E.T. Mathew S. Irudaya Rajan) Migration has been the single-most dynamic factor in the otherwise dreary development scenario of Kerala in the last quarter of the twentieth century. Kerala is approaching the end of the millennium with a little cheer in many people's homes, a major contributing factor for which has been migration. Migration has contributed more to poverty alleviation in Kerala than any other factor, including agrarian

reforms, trade union activities and social welfare legislation (K.C.Zachariah E.T. Mathew S. Irudaya Rajan) Kerala is in front in the experience of demographic transition compared to all other Indian states which manifests itself in quantum and model of both internal and international migration. Kerala is in the third stage of demographic transition. Demographic transition leads to an expansion of the working age population in the state and it leads to huge migration from the state to other parts of the nation and to other nations. On the other hand as a result of the demographic transition, the state is facing the problem of aging population. The 2011 census reveals that 60+ age group constitute about 12.6% of the state's total population as against 8.6% that of India and by 2061, it is estimated that this share would increase to 40% of Kerala's population.. The composition of aging population in total population and large outmigration from the state leads to the phenomenon of replacement migration in Kerala.

The fact or the concept of replacement migration is of recent origin. As a result of the demographic transition, turn down in working-age population or people to meet the required labour force along with increasing ageing population etc leads to the process of replacement migration. United Nations defines replacement migration as 'the migration that would be needed to offset declines in the size of population, the declines in the population of working age, as well as to offset the overall ageing of a population' (United Nations, 2000).

According to the 2011 Census, there are 457 million internal migrants in India. It accounting for 37.8 per cent of the total population and in Kerala this percentage was 48.9 per cent. One out of two persons in Kerala is an internal migrant. Over the years, Kerala's external (international) migrants were replaced by internal (in) migrants. According to the latest Kerala Migration Survey (2014) conducted by the Centre for Development Studies (CDS), Kerala has an estimated 2.4 million international migrants and 0.7 million internal migrants accounting for the absence of 3.1 million. Incidentally, the in-migrants to Kerala is estimated at 3.4 million in 2017 as per the GIFT (Gulati Institute of Finance and Taxation), which almost matches the quantum of internal and international migrants from Kerala giving rise to the phenomenon of "Replacement Migration" (Arun Perumbilavil Anand).

Objectives of the Study

- To analyze the phenomenon of migration in the state of Kerala;
- To recognize the reasons that are responsible for the evolution of replacement migration

An Overview of Migration in Kerala

Indian state of Kerala had received much attention in the 1970s and 1980s in view of the large number of emigrants to the gulf countries. The state has a work force of around 83 lakhs, out of which 19 lakhs are women workers. The vast majority work in the unorganised, or informal sector. Sometimes people work in conditions of partial employment, often without adequate access to decent wages or Social Security protection. The concentration of Government has been mainly focused on protecting the working conditions and the rights of the relatively privileged minority of workers in the organised sector.

Unemployment is one of the basic problems confronting the State, and Government has to spur the creation of new employment opportunities. There are presently around 43 lakhs of young people registered on the unemployment rolls of the State. Productive employment is being created in the State's economy at very low rates. Despite the relatively high skill and adaptability levels of the State's workforce, labour market has not been perceived as a positive factor by prospective investors in Kerala. The competitive market reform policies have turned many industrial units unviable. The plantation sector is also facing a grave situation due to unremunerative prices for commodity products like Coffee, Tea and Rubber. All this has led to retrenchment and closure of many industrial units and estates in the plantation sector.

Urbanization is one of the key "pull" factors of migration: "Contrary to conventional wisdom on urbanization and migration, high rates of migration (permanent and temporary) into urbanized areas have

continued despite rising levels of (formal) unemployment and persistent urban poverty. It shows that the expanding urban informal sector is representing a significant pull factor” (Deshingkar and Grimms, 2004). In many instances, large migrant population provokes substantial popular unease translated into xenophobia, racism, or lesser forms of hostility toward migrants. While the inflow of migrants has grown exponentially in recent years into the rapidly urbanizing and rapidly growing- South Western and Punjab Haryana- Delhi belt, policy makers have not woken up to this reality, except for knee-jerk reactions following Bangalore exodus, or Suzuki violence. It is politically imperative that policy makers pay attention to living conditions in the migrant centres.

External Migration

Migration has been a significant factor in helping reduce poverty and unemployment in Kerala. For over three decades there has been steady migration from the state of Kerala to countries in the Gulf and different parts of India and the world. It is estimated that today over 10 percent of the population of Kerala lives outside the state, in various parts of India and abroad particularly in the Gulf region, the US and Europe. According to the latest study ‘Kerala Migration Survey 2011’, 22.8 lakh Kerala emigrants are living abroad in 2011. The number of Kerala migrants living in other States of India in 2011 is estimated at 9.31 lakhs. There are two types of migration. They are external migration and internal migration. These are discussed below.

Internal Migration

A recent trend in the employment sector in the State is the inflow of interstate migrant labour from other States. Migrants are coming to Kerala from states like West Bengal, Bihar, Orissa, Chattisgarh, Jharkhand etc,. There are various factors leading to this in migration. They are

- Higher wages for unskilled labour in the State,
- Large opportunities for employment and
- Shortage of local labour,

These workers are less advantaged group in the labour market working for a subsistence living. Even though a comprehensive data on migrant labour is not available, different studies show that the incidence of migrant labour is increasing in the State. Since they are not engaged through a contractor or an intermediary, the legal protections envisaged under the Interstate Migrant Workmen (Regulation of Employment and Conditions of Service) Act, 1979 are alien to them in their employment. According to Census, 2001, among the districts, Ernakulam district, recorded the highest inflow of migrants from other States.

The migrant labourers get much higher monetary wages than in their native places and they work for longer hours and their real wages may be lower. They live in shanty houses/rooms in slums like localities often on a sharing basis. They have limited access to sanitation facilities and safe water and the working and living conditions and habits make them suffer from a number of diseases. But their access to public services like health and education is limited and they enjoy very limited protection from labour laws. They also face problems of social integration in Kerala.

Though these workers are predominantly engaged in the construction, plywood and steel industries, their presence is noticeable in almost all employments including service sector in the State. Because of their lower levels of reservation wages; and they do not have organization and union and lack of ‘voice’, recently there is an increasing tendency to employ migrant labour; especially in the field of constructions. Since measures had not been developed to improve the weak conditions of these labour, Social Security, compensation in case of job loss, health problems etc, the State Government have envisaged a scheme called “Inter State Migrant Workers Welfare Scheme” through Kerala Building and Other Constructions Workers Welfare Fund Board.

Non Resident Keralites

Non resident Keralites play a vital role in the development of the State. Their contribution to the development can be seen at family level, community level and state/country level. At family level it has improved household earnings, food, consumption, health care, housing and educational attainments and for over three decades remittances have been meeting the current account deficit of the country. The Non-Resident Malayali Census 2013 of Economics and Statistics Department, Government of Kerala, identified that out of the 16.25 lakh Non-Resident Malayalis, 14.26 are working in different jobs. Around 50 lakh people in Kerala are dependent on Non Resident Malayalis. Country wise, 90% of Non-Resident Malayalis are working in the Gulf region

As per the survey conducted by Economics and Statistics Department of Government of Kerala, the largest number of NRKs is reported from Malappuram, their proportion to the total NRKs being 18 per cent. Thrissur is in the second position accounting for 11per cent of the total followed by Kannur and Kozhikide with 10per cent share each. Idukki and Wayanad are the two low NRK reporting districts and their share to the total NRKs are 1per cent each.

Out of the total Non-Resident Keralites, 87.77per cent are engaged in different economic activities. Among those employed, 93.04per cent are men and 6.96per cent are women. District wise, Malappuram has the highest proportion of 19.51per cent NRKs employed followed by Thrissur and Kozhikode at 10.50per cent and 10.37per cent respectively. Even though Idukki reported the lowest share in employed NRKs women NRKs employed is 32.83per cent of total working women NRKs. Second highest proportion of female working NRKs is reported from Kottayam (31.68per cent).

Table Number of Emigrants and Its Change during 1998-2013

Year	Emigrants	Increase/Decrease
1998	1361919	--
2003	1838478	476559
2008	2193412	354934
2013	2400375	206963

Source: Kerala Migration surveys 1998-2013

According to the Kerala Migration Survey 2013, Kerala has 2.4 million emigrants compared to 1.4 million in 1998. Over last 20 years, emigration has augmented although exhibiting a gradual decline in its growth. About 4.7 lakh emigrants were estimated as new emigrants in 2003 compared to 1998. The inter-survey increase in 2003-2008 showed a decline with 3.5 lakh migrants compared to that in 1998-2003. Again there was a reduction in inter-survey estimates of 2.1 lakh over a five year period. Over the years there has been a drop in the number of emigrants and some districts witnessed a negative growth in terms of numbers. One of the probable reasons points to the global recession of 2008 that gripped the Gulf countries. Many people returned to their home state after losing their jobs during the crisis.

While looking at the phenomenon of Kerala's massive Gulf emigration, thus evolved and flourished from the latter half of the twentieth century onwards, it is obvious that in the initial phase the emigrants were predominantly non-agricultural labourers with low educational attainments. Nevertheless, the emigration of labour did not create any major hurdles and conspicuous deficiencies in the home economy in the early phase, but in later the continuous emigration resulted in a scarcity of labour especially in the construction sector, which was followed inevitably by a hike in the wage rate (Prakash, 1998). Interestingly, at present, Kerala has the highest wage rates among the states in India.

The chronic shortage of labour felt in the construction sector in Kerala and the resultant higher wage rates received the attention of workers from other states and they started flocking Kerala in large numbers. This

has opened a new era of replacement migration to Kerala as the state once again becoming a fertile ground for migrating population after a break of about 60 years since the 1960s. Though initially, the migrants were primarily from the states like Tamil Nadu and that mostly characterised seasonal and short-duration migration, at a later period the state started receiving migrants from far distant states like Bihar, Assam and West Bengal.

Demographic Transition and its Effect

District-wise Decadal Growth of Population by Residence and Sex in Kerala (2001-2011) (In Percentage)

Districts	Total		
	Persons	Male	Female
Kasaragod	8.58	6.89	10.19
Kannur	4.73	2.48	6.80
Wayanad	4.71	2.66	6.78
Kozhikode	7.20	5.12	9.16
Malappuram	13.45	11.73	15.06
Palakkad	7.35	7.30	7.40
Thrissur	4.94	4.13	5.69
Ernakulam	5.69	5.28	6.09
Idukki	-1.79	-2.45	-1.13
Kottayam	1.07	0.35	1.77
Alappuzha	0.88	-0.14	1.83
Pathanamthitta	-2.97	-4.70	-1.38
Kollam	1.94	-0.21	3.95
Thiruvananthapuram	2.07	0.75	3.32
Kerala	4.91	3.61	6.14

Source: Office of the Registrar General and Census Commissioner, India.

The above Figure depicts district wise decadal population growth rate experienced by Kerala during the period 2001 to 2011. Today the state experiences one of the lowest population growth rates in the country, i.e., only 4.91%. It is glaring to note that some districts of Kerala like Idukki (-1.93%) and Pathanamthitta (-3.12%) have stated witnessing population decline as per the recent census records. It is important to note that the state's population growth rate always remained higher than that of the India's until 1971. Since 1971, the population growth of the state started to decrease drastically marking the onset of demographic transition. So the demographic transition in Kerala leads to a shortage of labour force in Kerala now and in future.

District-wise Decadal Growth Rate of Child Population (Age Group 0-6 Years) by Residence in Kerala (2001-2011)

Districts	Total		
	Persons	Male	Female
Kasaragod	-2.01	-2.08	-1.94
Kannur	-1.96	-2.43	-1.47
Wayanad	-11.28	-11.53	-11.02

Kozhikode	-3.31	-3.83	-2.78
Malappuram	4.08	3.80	4.38
Palakkad	-5.20	-5.36	-5.03
Thrissur	-8.58	-8.20	-8.97
Ernakulam	-10.23	-10.51	-9.94
Idukki	-21.27	-21.08	-21.46
Kottayam	-17.94	-18.03	-17.84
Alappuzha	-15.18	-14.95	-15.41
Pathanamthitta	-23.76	-24.11	-23.41
Kollam	-13.10	-13.64	-12.55
Thiruvananthapuram	-16.68	-16.73	-16.62
Kerala	-8.44	-8.62	-8.26

Source: Office of the Registrar General and Census Commissioner, India.

The above figure shows that the District-wise Decadal Growth Rate of Child Population (Age Group 0-6 Years) by Residence in Kerala. It is clear from the table that, all district in kerala having negative growth rate its child population. This phenomenon is an outcome of the demographic transition in the state. This will leads to a The chronic shortage of labour in the state and in future the condition become serious.

Replacement Migration in Kerala

Replacement migration in Kerala simply means that the ones who have gone outside Kerala for job will be replaced by someone who came from outside Kerala. The relatively higher wages, large employment opportunities and shortages of local labours due to mass out migration, the changes in demography and resultant decrease in working age population make Kerala a lucrative job destination for workers from outside the State. This has made Kerala an emerging destination of internal migrants from other states in India, while Kerala continues to sending its own people as workers to the Middle East and Europe. At the same time, Kerala's lagging productive sectors and its major economic activities find a renewal with the current inflow of migrant workers to the state. The diverse roles played by the internal migrants to the state not only in terms supplementing its work force but also in terms of maintaining the vibrancy of state's economy have far reaching socio-economic implications.

In recent years, replacement migrants account for a significant proportion of workers in several sectors, especially among casual labourers in the construction sector. survey based study conducted by Gulati Institute of Finance and Taxation on behalf of the Department of Labour and Rehabilitation, Government of Kerala in 2013 estimated that there are over 25 lakhs inter-state migrants currently employed in the state with an annual arrival rate of 2.35 lakhs. This number constitutes about 9% of the State's total population. Moreover, the study also estimated that about Rs. 17,500 crores move out of the State in the form of remittances made by migrant labourers to their home states annually.

Conclusion

Migration as a component in interpreting demographic structure of the population has not been pronounced till recently. The process of demographic transition has been nearing its final stage, with fertility and mortality levels representing a near perfect replacement level of growth in population. Migration, both internal and international, together with the advances made with regard to demographic transition has undoubtedly been a distinct feature of the state of Kerala. A visible consequence of such distinction is its

share of elderly population which is one of the highest among Indian states (Rajan and Aliyar, 2012). As a result of the demographic transition, decline in working-age population or people to meet the required labour force due to huge out migration along with increasing ageing population etc leads to the process of replacement migration in Kerala. According to the Kerala Migration Survey 2013, Kerala has 2.4 million emigrants compared to 1.4 million in 1998. In the initial phase the emigrants from Kerala the migrants are predominantly non-agricultural labourers with low educational attainments. Nevertheless, the emigration of labour did not create any major hurdles and conspicuous deficiencies in the home economy in the early phase, but in later the continuous emigration resulted in a scarcity of labour especially in the construction sector, which was followed inevitably by a hike in the wage rate (Prakash, 1998). Interestingly, at present, Kerala has the highest wage rates among the states in India. The chronic shortage of labour felt in the construction sector in Kerala and the resultant higher wage rates received the attention of workers from other states and they started flocking Kerala in large numbers.

The relatively higher wages, large employment opportunities and shortages of local labours due to mass out migration, the changes in demography and resultant decrease in working age population make Kerala a lucrative job destination for workers from outside the State. At present, the in migrants in Kerala are replacing not only Gulf emigrant workers but also population deficits caused by the rapid fertility decline in Kerala which begun since the late 1960s.

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